

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND FBG MONITORING OF CURING-INDUCED STRAIN IN POLYMER COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The ability to predict strain evolution in polymer composites during the whole curing process is critical for the design of polymer composite structures. Hence, a large number of works concerning the viscoelastic behavior of polymer composites have been done. In this paper, in order to characterize the mechanical behavior of polymer composite laminates, a three-dimensional differential viscoelastic constitutive model including the effects of thermal expansion, chemical shrinkage and stress relaxation is established in ABAQUS. Also, the fiber Bragg grating (FBG) temperature and strain sensors are adjacently embedded in the laminate to monitor the temperature and strain evolution, and the monitored strain is evaluated by comparison with the simulated strain. The results reveal that the FBG temperature sensor can accurately reflect the actual temperature evolution in the laminate. Whereas the FBG strain sensor cannot effectively characterize the actual strain evolution at the early stage of cure due to low resin viscosity, movement of air and vapor bubbles as well as temperature undulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Because of high specific strength and stiffness, good corrosion resistance and outstanding designability, carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites have been widely used in many areas such as aerospace, sport equipment, vehicles and so on. However, the process-induced residual strain can deteriorate dimensional stability and durability of composite structures. Therefore, it is significant to predict and monitor the residual strain evolution during the fabrication of CFRP composites.

It is well known that polymer materials exhibit typical viscoelastic response during cure [1]. Ding [2] and Zobeiry [3] investigated the residual stress evolution of polymer composites using a three-dimensional differential viscoelastic model. The results revealed that the differential viscoelastic model was accurate and time-saving, and also more convenient to implement and code with finite-element method than the integral one. Hence, the differential viscoelastic model is adopted in this paper instead of the integral one.

In recent several years, due to its outstanding advantages such as the immunity to

electromagnetic interference, relative lightweight, durability, signal stability and suitability for wavelength multiplexing [4-7], the embedded fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors were widely used to provide in situ monitoring of composite materials without significant effects on the global mechanical behavior of the host material [8-11]. However, few works have been done to evaluate the effectivity of FBG monitoring of polymer composites during cure.

In this work, the strain evolution of the composite laminate during the entire cure cycle is numerically simulated. The embedded FBG temperature and strain sensors are used to monitor the temperature and strain evolution of the composite laminate. The monitored strain is evaluated by comparison with the corresponding simulated strain. The comparison can provide a comprehensive understanding of the thermocuring characteristics of polymer composites and the monitoring effectivity of FBG strain sensors.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The laminate embedded with FBG temperature and strain sensors was fabricated by means of hot press molding. The laminate consisted of 22 plies of TR50S/YPH-308 prepregs with the layup of $[90_{11}/0_{11}]$ and dimensions of $300\text{mm} \times 300\text{mm} \times 2.75\text{mm}$. The FBG temperature sensor (FBG-T) and FBG strain sensor (FBG-S) were located in the center of the 17th ply along the reinforcing fiber direction. The schematic diagrams of the CFRP laminate and embedded FBG sensors are presented in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1(a), the quarter geometry of CFRP laminate with the lengths of $a'=150\text{ mm}$, $b'=150\text{ mm}$ and $c'=1.375\text{ mm}$ is symmetric with respect to the x -axis and y -axis. The point G in Fig. 1(a) is used to represent the location where FBG sensors are embedded. Teflon tubes were used to protect the optical fiber from breaking in the egress location during the fabrication of the CFRP laminate. The temperature and strain sensitivity constants of FBG sensors were measured to be $9.6\text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$ and $1.2\text{ pm}/\mu\epsilon$, respectively.

Figure 1: Schematic diagrams of CFRP laminate and embedded FBG sensors. (a) Quarter geometry of CFRP laminate; (b) locally amplified sectional drawing of FBG-T and FBG-S.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The evolution of temperature and strain monitored by the FBG-T and FBG-S is depicted in

Fig. 2. As for the temperature evolution, although the temperatures at temperature dwells such as Dwell-1, Dwell-2, Dwell-3 and Dwell-4 are set to be constant in advance, the actual temperatures at all dwells exhibit frequent undulation, which can be attributed to two main reasons. The first is the internal heat generation due to the resin curing reaction, and the second is the imperfect temperature control stability of the industrial device.

As marked by the circle in Fig. 2, there is an obvious undulation existing at the beginning of cure, which mainly results from the impact from the mold closing process. Besides, the monitored strain exhibits the similar undulation to the monitored temperature at the corresponding temperature dwells except the Dwell-1. The evident strain fluctuation can be related to the temperature fluctuation.

Figure 2: Evolution of temperature and strain monitored by FBG sensors during the whole curing cycle.

Fig. 3 shows the comparison between monitored strain and simulated strain during cure. It can be observed that the monitored strain shows the evident differences from the simulated strain. The differences in strain are caused by the following two main factors. The first is the relatively weak bond strength between the resin and the grating at the early stage of cure, which makes the strain change of the resin not be transferred to the grating effectively. The second is the frequent temperature undulation and the movement of air and vapor bubbles under the conditions of high temperature and pressure. Besides, it can be seen from Fig. 3 that the curing degree of the resin becomes large enough during the Dwell-2, indicating that the strain of the resin can be transferred to the grating effectively. However, for the monitored strain, the frequent temperature undulation as well as the movement of air and vapor bubbles leads to the frequent strain undulation, and hence the chemical shrinkage strain cannot be displayed clearly. Apparently, the simulated strain tends to develop quickly during the Dwell-2.

Figure 3: Comparison between monitored strain and simulated strain during the whole curing cycle.

4 CONCLUSIONS

(1) The FBG temperature sensor can accurately reflect the actual temperature evolution in the laminate, and the monitored temperature can serve as the temperature condition of the numerical analysis.

(2) The FBG strain sensor cannot effectively monitor the actual strain evolution at the early stage of cure as a result of low resin viscosity, movement of air and vapor bubbles as well as temperature undulation.

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